

Environmental pre-emption and firm resilience: An analysis of listed Indian pharmaceutical firms

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Abstract

Environmental pre-emption is a key aspect of proactive environmental strategy. We argue that environmentally pre-emptive (EPr) firms develop superior informational and relational resources that help them manage inbound supply chains more effectively, making them resilient to input shocks during external disruptions. This resilience creates slack that enables continued investment in research and development (R&D). Using a difference-in-differences design on listed Indian pharmaceutical firms, and treating COVID-19 as a non-environmental exogenous shock, we classify as EPr those firms that proactively reduced carbon intensity in line with or beyond India's Nationally Determined Contribution commitments before the Paris Agreement. Our findings show that EPr firms experience significantly smaller increases in raw material cost intensity and significantly higher relative R&D spending during the pandemic compared to non-pre-emptive peers. The results highlight the broader benefits of environmental pre-emption, demonstrating its role in strengthening supply chain resilience and sustaining innovation during major disruptions.
